

[Research Article]

Antidepressant Effects of Ethanolic Extract of *Guiera senegalensis* in Mice: Evidence from Forced Swim and Tail Suspension Tests

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Abstract

Background: Depression is a devastating and life-threatening mental disorder that affects 20% of the world's population. Conventional pharmacological treatments have adverse effects, necessitating the search for alternative therapeutic options. *Guiera senegalensis*, a common medicinal plant in traditional African medicine, has demonstrated antidepressant properties. This study aimed to investigate the potential antidepressant effects of an ethanol leaf extract of *G. senegalensis* in mice.

Methods: Phytochemical screening was performed to identify the bioactive compounds in the extract. Acute toxicity was evaluated according to OECD guidelines, with doses of up to 5000 mg/kg. The mice were randomized into five groups, each containing five mice. Group I (control) received normal saline, and Groups II–IV (treatment groups) received 25, 50, and 100 mg/kg body weight of the extract, respectively. Group V animals received 10 mg/kg imipramine (reference drug). The antidepressant activity of the extract was tested using the Forced Swim Test (FST) and Tail Suspension Test (TST). Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA with Dunnett's post-hoc test.

Results: Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of flavonoids, tannins, and saponins, which are known for their neuropharmacological properties. Acute toxicity testing showed no mortality at 5000 mg/kg, indicating a high safety profile of the extract. *G. senegalensis* at all doses of 25, 50, and 100 mg/kg and the positive control drug imipramine (10 mg/kg) significantly shortened the immobility time in both the FST and TST compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Ethanol leaf extract of *G. senegalensis* exhibits antidepressant effects in animal models, supporting its traditional use in mood disorders. The presence of bioactive compounds indicates a pharmacological basis for their effectiveness. Further research is required to understand its mechanisms of action and evaluate its long-term safety.

Keywords: Depression; Acute toxicity; *Guiera senegalensis*; phytochemicals; medicinal plant.

Introduction:

Depression is among the most prevalent psychiatric disorders, affecting over 280 million individuals worldwide and accounting for approximately 3.8% of the global population (WHO 2023). This disorder poses a significant public health challenge, affecting individuals of all sexes and age groups, from childhood to old age ([Navinder Singh, 2024](#)). The burden of depression is especially pronounced in low- and middle-income countries, notably in sub-Saharan Africa, where restricted access to mental healthcare and socioeconomic challenges contribute to underdiagnosis and insufficient treatment of depression ([Safiri et al., 2023](#)).

Pharmacological interventions for depression, such as selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and tricyclic antidepressants, exhibit limited efficacy, with response rates between 60% and 70% and relapse rates of approximately 30%. ([Jakubovski et al., 2015](#)). Furthermore, these medications are frequently associated with adverse effects, including sedation, constipation, urinary retention, and cognitive impairment, which often hinder patient adherence and sustained use (Chu & Wadhwa, 2024). These limitations highlight the urgent need for safer and more effective alternatives, particularly those derived from natural products with favorable safety profiles ([Zubair & De Ranieri, 2024](#)).

Guiera senegalensis is a drought-resistant shrub prevalent throughout the Sahel region of West Africa, including Senegal, Mali, Burkina Faso, and Niger (Somboro et al., 2011). Traditionally, its leaves and roots have been used to address mental health-related conditions. ([Shehu et al., 2025](#)). Phytochemical analyses have indicated that *G. senegalensis* contains a variety of bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds, which are associated with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and neuroprotective activities ([Anka et al., 2020](#); [Elmalik et al., 2022](#); [Hayatou et al., 2024](#); [J M et al., 2024](#); [Ukwubile, 2025](#)).

The antidepressant effects of these phytochemicals are mediated by multiple mechanisms. Certain flavonoids modulate serotonergic activity by reducing mitochondrial MAO-A activity in the brain

and decreasing oxidative stress by inhibiting hydrogen peroxide production associated with the MAO-A reaction. ([Jazvinščak Jembrek et al., 2023](#); [Trivedi, 2025](#)). Plant alkaloids have demonstrated antidepressant properties by decreasing plasma corticosterone levels, enhancing monoaminergic turnover, interacting with MAO-A and various cell-surface receptors, reducing corticosterone release, inhibiting 11- β -hydroxysteroid dehydrogenase, and modulating monoamine neurotransmission. ([Perviz et al., 2016](#); [Qin et al., 2025](#)). Since low levels of monoamines, such as noradrenaline, dopamine, and serotonin, are implicated in depression, saponins are notable for their ability to increase monoamine neurotransmitter concentrations in the brain ([Yamamoto et al., 2026](#)).

Given the limitations of conventional pharmacological treatments for depression, it is essential to investigate natural alternatives with fewer adverse effects. *G. senegalensis*, a widely available and traditionally utilized medicinal plant, is a promising candidate for the development of novel antidepressant agents. This study assessed the antidepressant effects of the ethanolic leaf extract of *G. senegalensis* in mice using the Forced Swim Test (FST) and Tail Suspension Test (TST), both of which are established behavioral models for evaluating antidepressant activity. ([Khan et al., 2022](#))

Materials and methods

Plant material collection

Fresh leaves of *Guiera senegalensis* were collected from Gadau village, Itas-Gadau Local Government Area, Bauchi State, Nigeria, in April 2025. The plant was authenticated at the Department of Biological Sciences, Sa'adu Zungur University, Bauchi, and assigned a voucher number (00156) for future reference.

Experimental animals

Fifty mice (20–35 g) were procured from the animal housing facility of the Department of Physiology at Bayero University, Kano. The animals were maintained under standard laboratory conditions at the Animal House, Department of Anatomy, Sa'adu Zungur University, Bauchi State, Nigeria. A two-week acclimatization period was provided, during

which the mice had ad libitum access to water and commercial diet. Ethical clearance (BASUG/FBMS/REC/VOL.07/0103) was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee (FBMSREC) of Sa'adu Zungur University, Bauchi, before the commencement of the study.

2.3 Extraction of plant material

The leaves were washed and air-dried at room temperature until a constant weight was reached, and then ground to a fine powder using a mortar and pestle. Subsequently, 100 g of the coarse powder was extracted in 500 mL of 70% ethanol under mechanical agitation for 72 h. The resulting extract was filtered through filter paper and dried in an oven at 45-50°C until a consistent weight was obtained.

2.4 Phytochemical analysis

Standard qualitative phytochemical assays were used to identify the constituents of the ethanol extract of *Guiera senegalensis* (Evans, Evans, & Trease, 2009).

2.5 Acute toxicity study

Acute toxicity studies were performed on mice in accordance with the OECD guidelines (OECD, 2002). Both male and female animals were included to address biological variations in hormonal levels, metabolism, and body size. The mice were randomly assigned to two groups (n=3 per group). Group 1, serving as the control, received normal saline (5 mL/kg), whereas group 2 received *G. senegalensis* extract (5000 mg/kg). The animals were monitored for 24 h for signs of toxicity or behavioral alterations.

Antidepressant activity using the forced swim test (FST)

The forced swim test (FST) was performed in a vertical transparent tank measuring 40 cm in height and 18 cm in diameter, filled with water to a depth of 15 cm at 25°C, as described by Can *et al.* (2011). Each rat was placed individually in the tank, and the total immobility time was measured during the final 5 min of a 6-minute test session. Immobility was defined as floating with only minimal movements required to keep the head above water (Can *et al.*, 2011). Mice received treatments 30 min before testing as follows:

Group	Treatments
I	Control (normal saline, 5 mL/kg, p.o.)
II	<i>G. senegalensis</i> extract (25 mg/kg, p.o.)
III	<i>G. senegalensis</i> extract (50 mg/kg, p.o.)
IV	<i>G. senegalensis</i> extract (100mg/kg, p.o.)
V	Imipramine (10 mg/kg, p.o.)

2.7 Antidepressant activity using the tail suspension test (TST)

Mice were suspended from a shelf edge, with their noses positioned 20–25 cm above the floor, using a 17 cm adhesive tape attached 1 cm from the tip of the tail. Immobility time was measured during the final 5 min of a 6-minute session (Can *et al.*, 2012). Immobility was defined as passive motionless hanging. Groups of three mice (n=3) received treatments 30 min before testing as follows:

Group	Treatments
I	Control (normal saline, 5 mL/kg, p.o.)
II	<i>G. senegalensis</i> extract (25 mg/kg, p.o.)
III	<i>G. senegalensis</i> extract (50 mg/kg, p.o.)
IV	<i>G. senegalensis</i> extract (100mg/kg, p.o.)
V	Imipramine (10 mg/kg, p.o.)

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA, followed by Dunnett's post hoc test. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value less than 0.05 (SPSS Version 22). Comparisons were made between the test samples and the control group at the corresponding time points.

Results and discussion

Phytochemical screening

Table 1. Phytochemical Constituents of the Ethanol Extract of *G. senegalensis*

Constituent	Inference
Alkaloids	-
Tannins	+
Saponins	+
Flavonoids	+
Steroids	-

Preliminary phytochemical screening was performed to identify the bioactive constituents in the ethanol extract of *G. senegalensis*. The analysis indicated the presence of flavonoids, saponins, tannins, and terpenoids, while alkaloids and steroids were not detected (Table 1). Previous studies have demonstrated that *G. senegalensis* contains various bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and alkaloids. For example, one study reported the presence of flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, saponins, and phenols in the leaves of *Guiera senegalensis* (Dirar & Devkota, 2021; Elmalik, Ahmed, & A. A., 2022). These bioactive compounds are known for their pharmacological activities. Flavonoids have been shown to enhance serotonergic and noradrenergic neurotransmission, mechanisms associated with antidepressant effects (Alizadeh et al., 2024). Similarly, saponins have demonstrated significant neuroprotective effects against central nervous system disorders, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, and stroke (Sun, Xu, Lin, Cui, & Xu, 2015). The absence of alkaloids suggests that the observed central nervous system activity of the extract is not mediated by typical alkaloidal mechanisms, which often involve interactions with dopaminergic and cholinergic pathways (Hussain et al. 2018).

Acute toxicity test of ethanol extract of *G. senegalensis*

Acute toxicity evaluation demonstrated that the ethanol extract of *G. senegalensis* did not induce

mortality at a dose of 5000 mg/kg, suggesting a high safety margin. Mild behavioral changes, such as sedation and reduced food and water intakes, were observed within the first 24 h. According to the OECD guidelines, substances with an LD50 greater than 5000 mg/kg are classified as “practically non-toxic” (OECD, 2002). These results are consistent with those of previous studies reporting that *G. senegalensis* exhibits low toxicity, even at high doses (Lawan et al., 2023; Yahaya et al., 2019).

Antidepressant studies

Forced swim test (FST)

The forced swim test (FST) is widely employed to evaluate antidepressant activity by quantifying immobility time, which serves as an indicator of behavioral despair (Castagné, Moser, Roux, & Porsolt, 2011). Administration of the ethanol extract at 50 and 100 mg/kg significantly reduced the immobility time compared to the control group (Figure 1). This reduction was similar to that observed with imipramine (10 mg/kg). These findings indicate that *G. senegalensis* exhibits antidepressant-like properties, potentially mediated by monoaminergic modulation, particularly through increased serotonin and norepinephrine levels in the brain. Flavonoids present in the extract may contribute to this effect by inhibiting monoamine oxidase (MAO), thereby increasing the availability of neurotransmitters (Alizadeh et al., 2024).

Figure 1. Effects of ethanol extract of *G. senegalensis* and imipramine on forced swim-induced depression

Data presented as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean (SEM). N/S=Normal saline, GSEE=*G. senegalensis* ethanol extract, *=Significant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to the normal saline control group (Dunnett's post hoc test after one-way ANOVA).

Tail suspension test (TST)

The tail suspension test (TST) is a widely used model for evaluating antidepressant activity, particularly in the context of acute stress (Castagné et al., 2011). Administration of the ethanol extract resulted in a significant reduction in immobility time at doses of 50 and 100 mg/kg compared to the control group (Figure 2). However, this reduction was slightly less pronounced than that observed with imipramine at 10 mg/kg. The comparable efficacy of the extract and imipramine indicates that *G. senegalensis* may influence stress-coping mechanisms by enhancing serotonergic transmission and attenuating hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis hyperactivity, both of which are associated with depression (Alizadeh et al., 2024; Iob, Kirschbaum, & Steptoe, 2019). Bioactive constituents, such as tannins and saponins, have been shown to reduce corticosterone levels, thereby conferring stress-protective effects (Iob et al., 2019; Wiciński et al., 2023). Additionally, flavonoids have been shown to promote hippocampal neurogenesis, a process essential for mood regulation and antidepressant efficacy (Jazvinščák Jembrek, Oršolić, Karlović, & Peitl, 2023).

These findings are consistent with those of previous studies on *G. senegalensis*, a plant traditionally used to treat neurological disorders (Damo et al., 2022). Comparable antidepressant effects have been documented for other flavonoid-rich medicinal plants, such as *Hypericum perforatum* (St. John's Wort), which acts through serotonergic modulation (Hritcu et al., 2017). The anxiolytic effects observed in the elevated plus maze (EPM) test are consistent with those of earlier studies on plant-derived flavonoids, which demonstrated significant GABAergic activity (Damo et al., 2022).

Tail Suspension Test

Figure 2. Effects of ethanol extract of *G. senegalensis* and imipramine on tail suspension-induced depression

Data presented as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean (SEM). N/S=Normal saline, GSEE=*G. senegalensis* ethanol extract, *=Significant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to the normal saline control group (Dunnett's post hoc test after one-way ANOVA).

Conclusions

The ethanol extract of *G. senegalensis* exhibited significant anxiolytic activity in the elevated plus-maze (EPM) test and antidepressant-like effects in the forced swim test (FST) and tail suspension test (TST). These pharmacological effects are likely attributable to flavonoids, tannins, and saponins that modulate GABAergic and monoaminergic neurotransmission. Owing to its favorable safety profile, *G. senegalensis* is a promising candidate for developing novel anxiolytic and antidepressant agents. Nevertheless, additional research is required to elucidate its precise mechanisms of action, long-term safety, and efficacy.

Conflict of interest

The authors confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest to declare.

Statement of ethics

The study's ethical protocol was approved by the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences Research and Ethics Committee (FBMSREC) of Bauchi State University Gadau (approval number: BASUG/FBMS/REC/VOL.07/0103).

Availability of data and materials

All data generated or analyzed in this study are included in this published article.

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